

CROSS-CULTURAL PRAGMATICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: SPEECH ACTS AND POLITENESS STRATEGIES

Turgunova Sh.A.

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Abstract

This thesis investigates speech acts and politeness models in English and Uzbek, determining requests, apologies, and compliments. According to Austin (1962) and Searle's (1969) speech act theory, as well as Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness strategies, it analyzes how cultural norms, social hierarchy, and interpersonal connections can be reflected by linguistic choices. Based on various research, it is displayed that, English expresses explicit politeness markers integrated with indirectness, while Uzbek highlights contextual cues, honorifics, and culturally grounded indirectness to convey respect.

Keywords: politeness, pragmatics, speech acts, English, Uzbek, intercultural communication.

Speech acts play an important role in interpersonal relationships, which have different performs across cultures (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969). In English language, modal verbs and politeness markers are used to request something politely (e.g., *Could you please give me?*) to balance directness and friendliness (Blum-Kulka, 1987). Based on Uzbek language, however, it tends to honorific forms and culturally expected indirectness (e.g., *Bera olasizmi? Bora olasizmi?*) to remain social harmony (Turaev, 2018). In English, politeness level contains *very polite, polite, neutral / informal, impolite / rude* expressed with different modal forms, like *Could, Would, May I, Please, Can, Would you like ...etc.* For example:

Could you help me with this task, please? (Polite request; sounds soft and indirect)

Would you mind closing the window? (Polite inquiry/request)

May I ask you a question? (Very formal and respectful)

Could you pass the salt, please? (Politeness marker added to the request)

Can you help me with this box? (Common request, polite but more direct)

Would you like some coffee? (Offering politely)

In English language, apologies often start with an explicit acknowledgment of fault (*I'm sorry I am late*) followed by an explanation (Holmes, 1990). In Uzbek, expressions minimizing the offense are used (*Kechirasiz, noqulay bo'ldimi?*), to show a collectivist tendency to preserve the other person's face (Turaev, 2018).

Language	Apology Structure	Example Sentence
English	1. Acknowledgment of fault 2. Explanation (optional)	<i>I'm sorry I'm late. There was a lot of traffic.</i>
	1. Apology 2. Taking full blame	<i>I deeply apologize. It was entirely my mistake.</i>
	1. Apology + Reason	<i>Sorry I missed your call. I was in a meeting.</i>
Uzbek	1. Softened apology 2. Minimizing the offense	<i>Kechirasiz, noqulay bo'ldimi?</i>
	1. Indirect apology 2. Expression of inconvenience	<i>Xafa bo'lmang, bilmay qoldim.</i>
	1. Respectful tone 2. Implicit regret	<i>Uzr, ishlaringizga halal berdim shekilli.</i>

English compliments usually utilize appearance or achievements (You look great today!) and expect a simple “Thank you” response (Herbert, 1989). Compliments in Uzbek language may be met with modest deflection, which aligns with humility norms in Central Asian cultures (Rustamova, 2020).

Language	Compliment Style	Example Sentence
English	Compliment based on appearance or achievements	You look great today!
	Achievement-based compliment	Great job on the presentation!
Uzbek	Modest deflection or reciprocity	Rahmat, lekin siz ham chiroyli ko'rinyapsiz.
	Minimizing the compliment	Voy, unday emas, oddiygina kiyim-da.

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